

High Raised Sheep Farming: A Successful Livelihood Model for Rural Women

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Introduction

Livestock farming plays a vital role in strengthening the livelihood security of rural households. Among various livestock enterprises, sheep farming has emerged as a profitable venture due to its relatively low investment, quick returns, and high demand for mutton in the market. Adoption of scientific management practices can further enhance productivity and profitability. The success story of **Mrs. Nirmala Ramachandiran from Kodiyur village in Thanthoni Block of Karur District, Tamil Nadu**, demonstrates how scientific training and technical support can transform traditional sheep farming into a successful rural enterprise.

Profile of the Farmer

Mrs. Nirmala Ramachandiran is a graduate and previously worked as a lecturer in a school. Despite having a stable job, she had a strong interest in agriculture and livestock farming. Being from a rural background, she realized the potential of livestock enterprises in generating sustainable income for farm families. Motivated by this interest, she started a small sheep rearing unit mainly for meat production. Along with sheep farming, she also maintained **four milch cows and two calves** for milk production and explored opportunities in poultry farming for egg and meat production.

Problems Faced

During the initial stages of sheep farming, she encountered several constraints, including:

- Lack of scientific knowledge on sheep management
- Inadequate feeding and nutritional practices
- Poor housing facilities
- Limited knowledge on disease

prevention

- High lamb mortality in early stages

These challenges affected the productivity and profitability of the enterprise.

KVK Intervention

To overcome these issues, Mrs. Nirmala approached **Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK), Pulutheri** for technical guidance. The KVK scientists encouraged her to participate in training programmes on profitable sheep farming.

KVK Pulutheri organized training programmes on:

- Profitable Sheep Farming at Pulutheri – 19.06.2025
- Scientific Sheep Farming Practices at Aravakuruchi – 19.08.2025

Through these trainings, she gained knowledge on:

- High raised sheep housing systems
- Balanced feeding and mineral supplementation
- Scientific breeding management
- Lamb care and disease prevention
- Economic management of sheep farming

Technology Introduced

High Raised Sheep Housing

The high raised housing system helps to:

- Maintain better hygiene
- Reduce parasitic and infectious diseases
- Improve ventilation and comfort
- Facilitate easy manure collection

Milk Replacer Technology

To address the problem of early lamb mortality, **Milk Replacer Technology developed by the National Institute of Animal Nutrition and Physiology (NIANP)** was introduced by KVK scientists.

Benefits of milk replacer:

- Improves lamb nutrition during early life
- Enhances immunity
- Reduces lamb mortality
- Improves growth rate

Establishment of High Raised Sheep Farm

With the technical support of KVK Pulutheri, Mrs. Nirmala applied under the **National Livestock Mission (NLM)** scheme. She established a modern high raised sheep farm with financial assistance through a **bank loan of ₹1 crore along with 50% subsidy support.**

Impact of Technology Adoption

The adoption of improved housing and milk replacer technology significantly improved farm performance.

Parameter	Before Intervention	After Intervention
Average Lamb Body Weight	11 kg	15 kg
Lamb Survivability	70 %	90 %
Cost Benefit Ratio	3.05	3.72

The improvements clearly indicate that scientific interventions can greatly enhance productivity and profitability in sheep farming.

Recognition and Awards

In recognition of her dedication and success, **KVK Pulutheri honored Mrs. Nirmala Ramachandiran with the “Best Women Entrepreneur Award (High Raised Sheep Farming)” for the year 2025–26.**

Her achievements have motivated many farmers and rural women in the region to adopt scientific sheep farming practices.

Key Highlights of the Success Story

- Successful establishment of a **modern high raised sheep farm**
- Adoption of **scientific sheep farming practice**
- Reduction of lamb mortality through **milk replacer technology**
- Improvement in lamb body weight and survivability
- Enhanced profitability with **cost–benefit ratio of 3.72**
- Recognition as **Best Women Entrepreneur (2025–26)**

Conclusion

The success story of Mrs. Nirmala Ramachandiran highlights the crucial role played by **Krishi Vigyan Kendras in promoting livelihood opportunities through skill development and technology transfer.** Her transformation from a lecturer to a successful livestock entrepreneur serves as a powerful inspiration for rural women and youth to adopt scientific livestock farming for sustainable income generation.